

Enhancing grit among dentistry students of CEU Makati: A quasi-experiment

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The transition to online distance learning during the pandemic has underscored the role of grit in academic success. While existing research highlights its importance, limited studies explore interventions that enhance grit through intrapersonal factors. This study examines the grit levels of first-year Dentistry students at CEU Makati and evaluates whether an intervention can strengthen their perseverance. A quasi-experimental design was employed, with pre-test and post-test assessments using the Grit Scale to measure changes before and after a four-week online intervention. The programme included structured activities focused on fostering interest, deliberate practice, purpose, and hope – key components of grit. Due to lockdown restrictions, all sessions were conducted virtually. Nineteen students completed the programme, the majority of whom were female and aged nineteen. Results indicated no significant difference in grit scores between pre-test and post-test assessments, suggesting that the intervention did not produce measurable improvements in grit levels. However, findings suggest that Filipino college students already demonstrate resilience and perseverance despite academic and personal challenges. The lack of significant changes may be attributed to the short duration of the intervention, the nature of online delivery, or pre-existing grit levels among participants. These findings highlight the complexity of grit development and suggest that long-term, multifaceted interventions may be required for meaningful enhancement. Future research should employ longitudinal methodologies, incorporate diverse intervention strategies, and explore external factors influencing grit to better understand how perseverance can be effectively cultivated in academic settings.

Keywords: academic persistence; dentistry students; grit; intervention; resilience; student perseverance

University life presents numerous challenges that test students' perseverance and commitment. While each student's experience varies, many encounter obstacles that may hinder academic progress. Certain degree programmes, particularly those requiring board examinations, demand not only diligence but also resilience and endurance (Hoelterhoff et al., 2023). Dentistry, in particular, is recognised as a highly demanding field, requiring the acquisition of both technical competencies and interpersonal skills. Research has linked dental education to elevated stress levels, which can contribute to poor academic performance, burnout, and mental health concerns (Maderazo, 2017). Beyond academic demands, Dentistry necessitates self-discipline, sustained effort, and adaptability. The impact of COVID-19 lockdowns has further compounded these challenges. The transition from face-to-face to online learning posed difficulties for many students, particularly in adjusting to structural modifications such as the block system. Studies suggest that remote learning environments may hinder effective knowledge acquisition among Filipino students (Castro, 2022).

Although intelligence is traditionally considered a key determinant of academic success (Dandagal & Yarriswami, 2017; Giofre et al., 2017; Kumari et al., 2017), non-cognitive traits such as perseverance also play a significant role (Di Fabio & Palazzeschi, 2015; Parker et al., 2016; Smidt, 2015; Thomas et al., 2017). Angela Duckworth introduced the concept of grit, defining it as the passion and perseverance required in achieving long-term goals. Her research suggests that success is not solely dependent on cognitive ability; rather, grit may serve as a more reliable predictor of achievement (Duckworth, 2013).

Grit encompasses sustained effort and commitment despite setbacks or slow progress. This perspective shifts the focus from innate intelligence to the importance of persistence in overcoming academic challenges. The growing body of literature on grit underscores its relevance in education, particularly in fields requiring long-term commitment. Research indicates that dental students often experience physical and mental strain due to academic workload, leading to potential declines in performance (Araos et al., 2022). Additionally, a lack of motivation has been identified as a contributing factor to student attrition (Bibon, 2021). The shift to online learning during the pandemic has further emphasised the need to cultivate grit, given its positive association with academic performance (Salud, 2022).

Studies have established a strong correlation between grit, academic motivation, and overall achievement (Alhadabi & Karpinski, 2020; Karlen et al., 2019; Muenks et al., 2018). Given its demonstrated significance, grit is increasingly being examined within medical and healthcare education. However, research on whether grit can be developed through targeted interventions remains limited (Fawson et al., 2023; Hwang & Nam, 2021). Despite its recognised importance, few studies have proposed structured programmes to enhance grit (Mirza et al., 2021).

This study seeks to address this gap by examining grit levels among Dentistry students at CEU Makati and assessing the effectiveness of an intervention designed to strengthen perseverance. Additionally, it explores the role of the educational system in fostering grit at an early stage. The study is guided by Duckworth's (2016) framework, which identifies four key components in the development of grit: interest, practice, purpose, and hope.

Figure 1
Impact of the grit enhancement programme on pre-test and post-test results

Passion starts from appreciating what one does. People perform better and gain more satisfaction with their work when they are doing something that is in line with their personal interests. After a person discovers his or her interest, he or she must devote time for practice that will soon lead to mastery of the craft. Just because a person is interested in something, it does not mean that he or she is good at it immediately. Most people do not perform well with the things that trigger their interest. This is where practice comes in. For people to be able to perform well in their passion, they should spend hours diligently honing their craft. Practice does not mean quantity of time devoted to interest only, but also quality of time. Therefore, these passions and interests should be reinforced through deliberate practice. Furthermore, one form of perseverance is the discipline of improving and doing things better. What cultivates people's passion is their belief that what they are doing matters. The idea of purpose is the awareness that what they do matters to people other than themselves. Grit paragons say that even when the going gets tough or the obstacles seem too difficult to bear, their hardships and sacrifices are worth it because they know that at the end of the day, their efforts will benefit other people. Higher scores of purpose correlate with higher scores on the grit scale (Duckworth, 2016). Finally, there is hope. Hope is what makes gritty people rise up to the occasion whenever needed. It is the belief of a person that he or she can do something to change his situation. From the beginning to the very end, it is immensely significant for students to learn how to keep going even when all seems lost.

Thus, the researcher proposed to conduct a quasi-experimental study, as shown in Figure 1, which aimed to increase the level of grit among CEU Makati first year Dentistry students. In the programme, the researcher included activities intended to stimulate the four possible psychological sources of grit which are interest, practice, purpose, and hope (Duckworth, 2016). The pre-test was set as a baseline mean score for the level of grit. After the implementation of the Grit Enhancement Programme, a post-test was conducted to compare its mean score to that of the pre-test.

METHODOLOGY

Design

For this study, the researcher utilized a one-group pre-test, post-test quasi-experimental design to substantiate the effectiveness of the Grit Enhancement Programme developed by the researcher. There was no control group, and the researcher did not give random assignments. The researcher chose her participants by setting criteria and those who did not qualify were not included in the study. Participants were not confined to a single room during the conduct of the study and thus, some conditions were beyond the researcher's control. Grit scores from the pre-test were collected through Google Forms. Then, the participants underwent intervention via Zoom meetings to

increase their level of grit through the Grit Enhancement Programme. After this, the participants' grit scores from the post-test were collected through Google Forms and the outcome of the intervention was measured by comparing the pre-test and the post-test.

Participants

The researcher used purposive sampling for her study. The following criteria were set to select the participants: First, the participant must be a bona fide first year Dentistry student from CEU Makati; second, the participant must give his/her consent to participate in the study; third, the participant must respond to the Grit scale as a pre-test; fourth, the participant must be able to attend all four sessions of the programme; lastly, the participant must be able to respond to the Grit scale post-test. Students who were not able to meet the specified criteria were not included in the study. Participants of the study were bona fide first year college Dentistry students of CEU Makati who gave their consent to participate in the Grit Enhancement Programme.

Instrument

This study utilised the Grit Scale designed by Duckworth et al. (2007) to measure the perseverance and passion of an individual for long-term goals. The Grit Scale comes in a 12-item form. All items are quantified on a 5-point Likert scale. Scores range from 1 (not at all gritty) to 5 (extremely gritty). Internal consistency estimates (Cronbach's alpha) for the Grit Scale were 0.85. (Duckworth et al., 2007; Duckworth & Quinn, 2009). Pilot testing results showed internal consistency is acceptable with 0.70 administered to 116 samples. The researcher requested permission to use the Grit scale for her study. Duckworth recommended the 12-item version since it more fully represents the construct of grit. There are no published norms for any version of the scale to avoid reference bias.

Intervention

After the collection of data from the pre-test, the researcher conducted the Grit Enhancement Programme (GEP) which is centred on the four building blocks of grit - interest, deliberate practice, purpose, and hope.

The first session was about interest which emphasized how it plays a part in discovering our passion. The objective of the session was for the participants to appreciate their chosen course and develop an interest in learning. The first activity was called "I Like Dentistry because...". To engage the participants, the researcher utilized Mentimeter wherein participants were asked about what makes Dentistry appealing to them as a career, which influenced them to take up Dentistry, and how much they appreciate Dentistry. Participants were also asked to express their experience as a freshman Dentistry student through writing in a journal and reflect how it meets their expectations. Another activity is called Connect where participants were given a list of their subjects and then were asked to explain how each subject helped them become successful in their chosen career. The short lecture discussed the benefits of having Dentistry as a career and strategies on how to make learning more enjoyable.

The second session was about deliberate practice which highlighted that persistence and quality practice is more important than spending longer hours in aimless practice. The objective of the session was to demonstrate what deliberate practice is and how the participants can achieve it

through proper goal-setting and focused attention. In one activity, the participants were presented with two players who both practiced for 100 hours with different conditions and then later asked to explain which player would be better. Another activity is mindfulness meditation where participants were shown a video of guided meditation and were asked to do the same. The short lecture pointed out the conditions of deliberate practice and cited approaches to improve mental focus.

The third session was about purpose which pointed out that having the intention to contribute to the welfare of others helps sustain our passion. The objective of the session was to assist participants to recognize their intrinsic motivations and understand one's connection to a broader society. The Parable of Bricklayers was presented as an activity wherein students were shown how the three bricklayers viewed their work differently and how it affected their level of satisfaction. This is to show that the true meaning of life lies in being passionate about a specific purpose. The lecture discusses strategies on how participants can contemplate on their purpose in life. Ideal world is an activity that promotes participants to describe their ideal world and reflect if their actions contribute to achieve it.

The last session was about hope which aimed to develop optimism and foster growth mindset among the participants. For the activity, a video about learned helplessness theory and how our beliefs about success and learning affect our perception of challenges which results to pessimistic behaviour. Another video presented the benefits of having a positive outlook in life and necessary actions one can take to become an optimist. The lecture discussed what is fixed and growth mindset. Participants were also taught ways on how they can reframe their perspective about life and how they can take control of their situation during difficult times.

The researcher strictly observed the protocols for the conduct of this study. Proper authorities were informed and she requested permission to conduct the study on their students. Lastly, the participants' consent was obtained before conducting the study. They were informed of the objectives of the study, and how it will run, assured confidentiality of their responses and identities, and emphasized that their participation in the study was voluntary.

RESULTS

Data was analysed using the following statistical tools: paired t-test, mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage.

Table 1 shows the level of grit among the first-year Dentistry students before the conduct of the intervention. The results of their grit scores show that 73.68% or many of the students were gritty, a few, or 10.53% of the population were somewhat gritty, while some of the students, or 15.79% were already extremely gritty.

Table 1
 Distribution of grit levels and summary statistics (before the intervention)

Grit Levels	f	%
Extremely Gritty	3	15.79
Gritty	14	73.68
Somewhat Gritty	2	10.53
Total	19	100.00
Mean	3.59	
Average	0.435	
Overall Grit Level	Gritty	

Table 2 presents the level of grit among the first year Dentistry students after they completed the programme intervention. It shows that the majority of the participants were gritty with 84.21%, and few students were somewhat gritty with 5.26 percent, while some students were extremely gritty with 10.53%.

Table 2
 Distribution of grit levels and summary statistics (after the intervention)

Grit Levels	f	%
Extremely Gritty	2	10.53
Gritty	16	84.21
Somewhat Gritty	1	5.26
Total	19	100.00
Mean	3.59	3.59
Average	0.433	
Overall Grit Level	Gritty	

Table 3 presents the comparison between the levels of grit between the participants before and after the conduct of the Grit Enhancement Programme. Results of the means from the grit scores before and the grit scores after the conduct of the programme showed no significant difference.

Table 3
 Comparison of the Grit Scores before and after the Intervention

	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Grit score (before)	3.589	.4345	.000	1.000
Grit score (after)	3.589	.4332		

DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicate that the Grit Enhancement Programme did not yield statistically significant changes in the grit scores of first-year Dentistry students at CEU Makati. While previous research has established the importance of grit in academic achievement (Duckworth et al., 2007; Eskreis-Winkler et al., 2014), the findings of this study suggest that short-term interventions may not be sufficient to cultivate measurable improvements in perseverance and passion for long-term goals. Several possible explanations for these findings warrant discussion.

One potential reason for the lack of significant differences between pre-test and post-test scores is the pre-existing grit levels of the participants. The majority of students were already classified as gritty prior to the intervention, which may have created a ceiling effect that limited the potential for further improvement. This aligns with studies suggesting that individuals who already possess high levels of grit may not exhibit substantial changes through short-term interventions (Kannangara et al., 2018). Additionally, cultural factors may play a role, as Filipino students have been found to demonstrate resilience despite academic and personal challenges (Bibon, 2021).

Another critical factor is the duration of the intervention. The four-week online programme, while structured around Duckworth's (2016) four components of grit – interest, deliberate practice, purpose, and hope – may not have been long enough to facilitate meaningful changes in behaviour and mindset. Research indicates that the development of non-cognitive traits such as grit requires prolonged and consistent reinforcement (Alan et al., 2019). Future interventions should consider extending the duration of programmes and incorporating repeated exposures to grit-building activities over an extended period.

The online delivery format may also have influenced the outcomes. While virtual learning environments have become increasingly prevalent, they present unique challenges in engagement and interaction. Studies have suggested that face-to-face interventions may be more effective in fostering perseverance and motivation due to the presence of direct social interactions, real-time feedback, and hands-on activities (Aller et al., 2022). Future research should explore whether in-person interventions yield different results, as well as examine hybrid models that combine online and face-to-face elements.

Moreover, grit is a complex construct influenced by both individual and environmental factors. While the intervention focused on intrapersonal strategies, external influences such as family

support, peer relationships, and institutional structures also play a significant role in grit development (Hwang & Nam, 2021). Future studies should explore how integrating environmental support systems into intervention strategies may enhance their effectiveness. For example, parental involvement, mentorship, and academic advising could complement structured grit-training programmes.

Lastly, the measurement of grit remains a subject of ongoing debate. While the Grit Scale is a widely used tool, some researchers argue that self-report measures may be susceptible to biases such as social desirability and response tendencies (Credé et al., 2017). Future research may benefit from employing mixed-method approaches, including qualitative interviews and behavioural assessments, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of changes in grit over time.

Despite the lack of statistically significant changes, this study contributes valuable insights into the challenges and considerations in designing grit interventions. The findings suggest that while grit can be fostered through structured programmes, achieving measurable improvements may require a multifaceted approach that considers duration, delivery mode, and external support systems. Future research should build on these findings by employing longitudinal designs, incorporating diverse intervention strategies, and examining external influences on grit development in academic settings.

CONCLUSION

Although the intervention did not have a significant impact on the level of grit among the participants, it is noticeable that the results of the pre-test and post-test of the students suggest that Filipino college students are gritty. Thus, it can be presumed that despite the difficulties encountered in school and within their personal life, they are capable of coping and functioning daily. The current study is not without limitations. For starters, the study's sample was limited to first year Dentistry students from one university and therefore, the findings cannot be applied to all Dentistry students in the country or abroad. Also, the researcher did not have full control over the participants which makes the study vulnerable to extraneous variables that affected the outcome. Thus, more research is needed to substantiate the current study's conclusions.

Based on the results derived from the study, it is recommended that other researchers may consider using other research design such as mixed method wherein they assess who are gritty and those who are not. Afterward, they can conduct an interview with students who have high levels of grit to design an intervention for those who scored low on grit. For the programme, intervention strategies could involve cognitive, behavioral, and emotional domains of grit. Aside from intrapersonal conditions used in the study, the intervention should also involve environmental conditions such as parenting and learning experience. Intervention sessions can be done face to face and in small groups. The number of sessions can be at least five or more, usually lasting 40–60 min, and are mostly held at weekly intervals. To better integrate the information that was shared and discussed, it is advisable to have adequate time and frequency of meetings. After each session, it may also be useful to provide handouts highlighting the salient topics discussed during that particular session for better understanding and reference material. Future studies using rigorous and longitudinal designs are also recommended.

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